

Case Report

Physiotherapy-induced functional recovery in a non-ambulatory elderly patient with bilateral knee osteoarthritis: a case report

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Abstract

Background: Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is one of the most common musculoskeletal disorders affecting older adults and is frequently associated with chronic pain, muscle weakness, impaired mobility, and progressive functional decline. In very elderly individuals, these impairments may lead to loss of independence and increased dependency for activities of daily living. Physiotherapy plays an important role in the conservative management of knee OA by improving muscle strength, joint stability, and functional mobility. **Case report:** This case report describes the functional recovery of an elderly patient with severe mobility limitation secondary to bilateral knee OA following a structured physiotherapy rehabilitation programme. **Case summary.** An 86-year-old male with a diagnosis of bilateral chronic knee osteoarthritis presented with severe generalized knee pains and weakness, inability to ambulate, and dependence on caregivers for basic transfers and most activities of daily living. The patient also demonstrated reduced trunk balance and control, poor standing tolerance, and marked limitations in functional mobility. The patient underwent a structured home-based physiotherapy rehabilitation programme for a period of ten weeks. Following the intervention, the patient demonstrated marked functional improvement. He was able to maintain independent sitting posture for extended periods, showed improved trunk and limb muscle strength, achieved standing tolerance of approximately four minutes, and regained the ability to ambulate using a walking frame. **Conclusion:** This case highlights the potential benefits of structured physiotherapy rehabilitation in improving mobility and functional capacity in very elderly patients with severe bilateral knee osteoarthritis. Even in advanced age with significant functional limitations, targeted physiotherapy interventions can lead to meaningful recovery of mobility and independence in a cost-effective manner with limited use of pharmacological agents or medications. Being a single case study, further studies involving larger patient populations are recommended to support these findings.

Keywords: functional mobility, gait rehabilitation, geriatric physiotherapy, knee osteoarthritis, muscle strengthening.

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Introduction

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is one of the most prevalent degenerative joint disorders affecting older adults worldwide ¹⁻³ and represents a major cause of pain, disability, and reduced quality of life in the ageing population. ⁴⁻⁶ The incidence and severity of knee OA increase with advancing age due to progressive degeneration of articular cartilage, joint space narrowing, and alterations in subchondral bone. ^{7,8} These pathological changes often manifest clinically as joint pain, stiffness, reduced range of motion, and impaired functional mobility. ^{3,5,6}

In elderly individuals, the functional limitations associated with knee OA are frequently exacerbated by age-related physiological changes such as sarcopenia, reduced muscle strength, decreased balance, and diminished cardiovascular endurance. 1,9 These factors collectively contribute to increased dependency in activities of daily living (ADLs), heightened fall risk, and progressive loss of independence.^{7,10}

Physiotherapy is widely recommended as a key component of conservative management for knee osteoarthritis, with exercise-based rehabilitation programs shown to improve pain, muscle strength, and functional mobility. 1,11 However, most clinical studies evaluating the effectiveness of physiotherapy interventions for knee OA have focused on relatively younger elderly populations or ambulatory individuals. 12,13 Evidence regarding rehabilitation outcomes in advanced aged patients with severe functional decline or complete loss of ambulation remains limited. In clinical practice, patients of advanced age who become non-ambulatory due to musculoskeletal disorders are often perceived as having limited rehabilitation potential. Consequently, rehabilitation intervention may be less aggressively pursued in this population due to concerns about frailty, comorbidities, and reduced physiological reserve. This creates a clinical dilemma for healthcare professionals regarding the potential benefits of structured physiotherapy for very elderly individuals with profound mobility limitations. This case report describes the functional recovery of an 86 year old male with bilateral knee osteoarthritis, severe generalise weakness, and non ambulatory status who underwent a structured physiotherapy rehabilitation programme. He was a retire civil servant and an athlete tennis specialist.

The report highlights the potential role of targeted physiotherapy interventions in improving mobility and functional independence in advance age with significant musculoskeletal impairment.

Case Presentation

Patient Information

An 86-year-old retired male was referred for physiotherapy management due to progressive bilateral knee pain, stiffness, and severe mobility limitation. The patient reported a long-standing history of knee discomfort that had gradually worsened over several years. In the months preceding referral, his functional status had significantly deteriorated, resulting in inability to ambulate and increasing dependence on caregivers for mobility and activities of daily living. He was to be dependent on oral analgesic but has had few sessions of physiotherapy about 3 years prior to referral with moderate improvement. The patient had six (6) year medical history of controlled hypertension and age-related generalized muscle weakness. He was of normal weight body mass index (22.7kg/m²). 14 There was no history of recent trauma, surgery, or neurological disease. Prior to the progression of symptoms, the patient had been able to ambulate independently within his home environment.

Clinical Findings at Baseline

At the initial physiotherapy assessment, the patient presented with marked functional impairment and generalized physical deconditioning.

He reported severe bilateral knee pain during movement, rated approximately 7/10 on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) worsen by attempted weight bearing or ambulation. Clinical examination revealed restricted knee joint range of motion in both flexion (-20⁰) and extension (-10⁰), accompanied by observable quadriceps muscle weakness.

Manual muscle testing demonstrated generalized muscle weakness affecting both upper and lower extremities, with lower limb strength graded approximately 2-3/5 on the Medical Research Council (MRC) scale. Trunk stability was significantly compromised, as the patient was unable to maintain unsupported sitting for more than 10 seconds without losing postural control. Functional mobility was severely limited. The patient was unable to stand independently and required maximal assistance for transfers. He was non-ambulatory at presentation and demonstrated poor cardiovascular endurance, becoming easily fatigued with minimal physical activity.

Functional Status

The patient was highly dependent on caregivers for most activities of daily living, including transfers, mobility, and basic self-care tasks. His overall physical condition suggested significant deconditioning secondary to prolonged inactivity and progressive musculoskeletal impairment.

Therapeutic Goals

Based on the initial assessment, the primary rehabilitation goals were to:

1. Improve lower limb muscle strength, particularly the quadriceps and hip extensors
2. Enhance trunk control and sitting balance
3. Increase sitting tolerance and ability to maintain upright posture
4. Achieve safe standing and eventual ambulation with an assistive device
5. Improve cardiovascular endurance and activity tolerance
6. Promote greater independence in transfers and basic activities of daily living

Intervention

Over a period of ten (10) weeks (five sessions per week, each 45-60 minutes), the following programme was delivered (Table 1). 3 of the 5 weekly visits were supervised and monitored by a team of physiotherapist.

1. Pain/Joint Mobility Management: Application of superficial and/or deep (therapeutic ultra sound and/or moist heat) heat before therapy, gentle passive/active-assisted knee ROM exercises.
2. Progressive Strengthening:
 - Isometric quadriceps and gluteal sets progressing to isotonic knee extensions, hip extensions and

seated leg presses (as tolerated). Ten repetitions of 3 sets are performed at each session.

- Upper-limb strengthening via seated resistance exercises (to support transfers and frame use)
3. Trunk Control & Balance:
 1. Seated trunk activation (e.g., pelvic tilts, upright sitting with minimal support)
 2. Supine bridging and trunk stabilisation exercises
 4. Functional Training:
 1. Sit-to-stand practice on an armed chair measuring 0.4M from the ground (initial assisted, progressing to minimal assistance)
 2. Standing balance with frame support; static then dynamic tasks
 3. Gait re-education: stepping strategies, weight shifting, walking frame ambulation initiation under supervision
 5. Cardiorespiratory Conditioning: Seated marching, controlled breathing, low-intensity endurance tasks with monitoring of fatigue and vital signs
 6. Home Exercise Programme (HEP). Exercises sessions including knee flexion/extension, quadriceps sets, trunk sitting drills and assisted walking with frame (under supervision/with safety). This is used to augment treatments on days that the treatment team does not visit the patient home.

Therapy progression was based on tolerance, vital signs monitoring, pain response and functional improvement.

Outcomes

Following ten weeks of structured physiotherapy rehabilitation, the patient demonstrated substantial improvement in functional mobility, muscle strength, and postural control.

At the beginning of the intervention, the patient was non-ambulatory and unable to maintain independent sitting posture for prolonged periods. By the end of the rehabilitation programme, the patient was able to sit independently with improved trunk stability and maintain upright sitting posture without support.

Table 1. Intervention protocol

	Pre-intervention assessment/outcomes	Outcome measures	Interventions	Post-intervention outcomes
1 st to 2 nd weeks	Pain: VAS - 8/10; ROM: Flexion - 20; Extension - 10	-VAS -Goniometry	Pain relief: ultrasound therapy; infrared radiation ROM Exercise: gentle passive exercise	VAS: 5/10 ROM -Flexion: -15 -Extension: -8
3 rd to 4 th weeks	Pain: VAS - 5/10; ROM: Flexion -15; Extension - 8; Strength: MRCS - 2/5	-VAS -Goniometry -MRCS	Pain relief: ultrasound therapy; infrared radiation ROM Exercise: free active exercise Progressive strengthening exercise:	VAS: 3/10 ROM -Flexion: - 12 -Extension: - 5 MRCS - 3/5
5 th to 6 th weeks	Pain: VAS - 3/10; ROM: Flexion - 12; Extension - 5; Strength: MRCS - 3/5; Poor Trunk & Balance Control	-VAS -Goniometry -MRCS	Pain relief: ultrasound therapy; infrared radiation ROM Exercise: Free active exercise with weight Progressive strengthening using 2kg weight Sit to stand exercise, Seated trunk activation & supine bridging exercises	VAS: 2/10 ROM -Flexion: - 10 -Extension: - 2 MRCS: 3+/5
7 th to 8 th weeks	Pain: VAS - 2/10; ROM: Flexion - 10; Extension - 2; Strength: MRCS - 3+/5; Poor Trunk & Balance Control	-VAS -Goniometry -MRCS	Pain relief: ultrasound therapy ROM Exercise: Free active exercise with weight Progressive strengthening exercise using 3kg weight Sit to stand exercise, seated trunk activation & supine bridging exercises	VAS: 1/10 ROM -Flexion: - 5 -Extension: full range MRCS: 4/5
9 th to 10 th weeks	Pain: VAS - 1/10; ROM: Flexion - 5, Extension - full range Strength: MRCS - 4/5; Poor trunk & balance control	VAS Goniometry MRCS	Pain relief: infrared radiation ROM Exercise: free active exercise with weight Progressive strengthening exercise using 3.5kg Sit to stand exercise, seated trunk activation, supine bridging exercise	VAS: 1/10 ROM -Flexion: - 5 -Extension: full range MRCS: 4/5 Function, Trunk & balance control: sit independently with upright posture, stand for 4minutes and ambulate using walking frame on flat surface

Key: VAS - Visual Analogue Scale, ROM - Range of Motion, MRCS - Medical Research Council Scale

Muscle strength in the lower extremities showed noticeable improvement (4/5), particularly in the quadriceps muscles, which contributed to enhanced knee stability during weight-bearing activities. The patient was also able to achieve supported standing with improved balance and was capable of maintaining standing posture for approximately four minutes.

Most notably, the patient regained the ability to ambulate using a walking frame on a flat surface within his sitting room, marking a significant improvement from his initial non-ambulatory status. His tolerance for physical activity also improved, with reduced fatigue during functional tasks.

These functional gains translated into greater independence in basic mobility and transfers, thereby reducing the level of caregiver assistance required for daily activities. The patient reported subjective improvement in confidence and mobility within the home environment.

No adverse events were reported during the course of the physiotherapy intervention.

Discussion

This case report describes the functional improvement of an 86-year-old patient with bilateral knee osteoarthritis and severe mobility limitation following a structured physiotherapy rehabilitation programme. At baseline, the patient presented with profound functional impairment characterized by severe knee pain, generalized muscle weakness, poor trunk stability, inability to stand independently, and complete loss of ambulation. After ten weeks of progressive physiotherapy intervention, the patient demonstrated significant improvements in sitting balance, standing tolerance, lower limb strength, and the ability to ambulate using a walking frame. Knee osteoarthritis is a major contributor to disability among older adults and is frequently associated with reduced mobility and loss of independence. The degenerative changes that occur in the knee joint often lead to pain, stiffness, and reduced joint range of motion, which in turn limit physical activity. Reduced activity levels may further contribute to muscle atrophy, decreased endurance, and impaired balance, thereby creating a cycle of progressive functional decline. In very elderly individuals, these limitations are often compounded by age-related physiological changes such as sarcopenia, reduced neuromuscular

coordination, and decreased cardiovascular capacity.

Physiotherapy interventions focusing on muscle strengthening, balance training, and functional mobility exercises have been widely recommended for the conservative management of knee osteoarthritis.^{1,15,16} Strengthening of the quadriceps muscles is particularly important because quadriceps weakness has been strongly associated with knee instability, increased joint loading, and worsening functional limitations in individuals with knee OA. In the present case, progressive strengthening exercises targeting the quadriceps and other lower limb muscles likely contributed to improved joint stability and enhanced ability to perform weight-bearing activities.

Another important component of the rehabilitation programme was trunk stabilization and postural control training.^{17,18} Impaired trunk control can significantly affect sitting balance and functional mobility in elderly individuals. Improvements in trunk stability observed in this patient enabled him to maintain independent sitting posture and provided a stable foundation for subsequent standing and gait training. This highlights the importance of incorporating core stability exercises in rehabilitation programmes for elderly patients with severe functional decline.

The gradual introduction of functional task-oriented training, including sit-to-stand practice, supported standing, and gait training with an assistive device, was also a key aspect of the intervention. Task-specific training is known to promote neuromuscular adaptation and improve the transfer of therapeutic gains to real-life functional activities. In this case, the patient progressed from being completely non-ambulatory to walking with a frame, which represents a clinically meaningful improvement in mobility and independence.

The findings of this case report also underscore the potential benefits of rehabilitation even in very advanced age. Patients in their eighth or ninth decade of life are sometimes perceived as having limited rehabilitation potential due to frailty and multiple comorbidities. However, the improvements observed in this patient demonstrate that appropriately tailored physiotherapy interventions can still produce meaningful functional gains in very elderly individuals. Restoring the ability to stand and ambulate, even with assistive devices, may

significantly enhance quality of life, reduce caregiver burden, and lower the risk of complications associated with prolonged immobility such as pressure ulcers, muscle wasting, and reduced cardiovascular fitness.

Despite these encouraging outcomes, certain limitations should be acknowledged. As a single case report, the findings cannot be generalized to all patients with knee osteoarthritis. Individual factors such as motivation, baseline functional status, comorbid conditions, and adherence to therapy may influence rehabilitation outcomes. Additionally, the absence of standardized outcome measures such as functional mobility scales or validated quality-of-life assessments limits the ability to quantitatively evaluate the magnitude of improvement. Future studies involving larger samples and standardized outcome measures are therefore recommended to further investigate the effectiveness of physiotherapy interventions in very elderly patients with severe functional limitations due to knee osteoarthritis.

Implications for clinical practice

This case supports the notion that age alone should not preclude intensive, tailored physiotherapy aimed at mobility restoration in older adults with OA and weakness. Clinicians working in geriatrics should consider incorporating strength, trunk control, balance and mobility re-education, even in severely limited patients, and closely monitor progress. Future research in larger cohorts (case series or controlled studies) is warranted to explore optimal dose, modality and long-term maintenance strategies.

Conclusion

In summary, the intervention yielded marked functional improvement in an 86-year-old male with bilateral knee osteoarthritis and generalized weakness, conveying that meaningful recovery is feasible in geriatric physical therapy contexts. Continued rehabilitation and monitoring are recommended to consolidate gains and facilitate further mobility improvements.

Ethical Considerations

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient (and family) for publication of this case report in anonymised form. All procedures were in accordance with institutional ethical standards and with the principles of the World Health Organization's Declaration of Helsinki.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author contribution

Babangida Shehu Bappah, Abdulkadir Hussaini Gwarzo, Adamu Muhammad Sabo were involved in administering the treatment. Babangida Shehu Bappah, Abdulkadir Hussein Gwarzo, Lawan Umar, Buhari Hassan, Suleiman Mohammed, Buhari Abdullahi Tafida gave substantial contribution to conception and design. Babangida Shehu Bappah, Adamu Muhammad Sabo, Adamu Usman Gamawa, Buhari Hassan, Buhari Abdullahi Tafida, Lawan Umar and Abdulkadir Hussein Gwarzo drafted and critically revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript for publication.

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